

D1.5 – Data Integration Interfaces for Building Industry using BIM and Digital Building Twins

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Abstract

This document describes the interaction between the back end of the BIMprove digital twin with the internal and external clients to exchange data.

Main connections are described towards 6 different cases.

Keywords

Digital Twin, Data integration, services, interfaces, data services, API

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
BIM	Building Information Modelling
API	Application Programming Interface
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
BCF	BIM Collaboration Format
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
HTTP	Hypertext Transport Protocol
GUID	Globally Unique Identifier
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol

BIMprove project

In the past 20 years, productivity in the European construction industry has increased by 1% annually only, which is at the lower end compared to other industrial sectors. Consequently, the sector has to step up its digitization efforts significantly, on the one hand to increase its competitiveness and on the other hand to get rid of its image as dirty, dangerous and physical demanding working environment. Construction industry clearly needs to progress beyond Building Information Modelling when it comes to digitizing their processes in such a way that all stakeholders involved in the construction process can be involved.

The true potential of comprehensive digitization in construction can only be exploited if the current status of the construction work is digitally integrated in a common workflow. A Digital Twin provides construction companies with real-time data on the development of their assets, devices and products during creation and also enables predictions on workforce, material and costs.

BIMprove facilitates such a comprehensive end-to-end digital thread using autonomous tracking systems to continuously identify deviations and update the Digital Twin accordingly. In addition, locations of construction site personnel are tracked anonymously, so that **BIMprove** system services are able to optimize the allocation of resources, the flow of people and the safety of the employees. Information will be easily accessible for all user groups by providing personalized interfaces, such as wearable devices for alerts or VR visualizations for site managers. **BIMprove** is a cloud-based service-oriented system that has a multi-layered structure and enables extensions to be added at any time.

The main goals of **BIMprove** are a significant reduction in costs, better use of resources and fewer accidents on construction sites. By providing a complete digital workflow, BIMprove will help to sustainably improve the productivity and image of the European construction industry.

Contents

1. Introduction.....	7
2. Maturity Levels	7
3. Services.....	8
3.1. Mature / Bimsync.....	8
3.2. Experimental / Geometry	8
3.3. Experimental / BIM Extended	8
3.4. Experimental / Localization.....	9
3.5. Experimental / Images	9
3.6. Custom / Risk	9
3.7. Custom / UXVs	10
4. Overview	11
4.1. Annuli of Maturity.....	11
4.2. Internal Service Communication.....	11
5. Data Management.....	12
5.1. Anonymization of personal data	12
5.2. Authentication	12
5.3. Authorization.....	12
Annex A Schematic of three examples.....	13
E1: Truck Guidance	13
E2: Deviation As-planned <i>versus</i> As-built	14
E3: On-site Risk Alert.....	15

Index of Figures

Figure 1: Visualisation of maturity levels.....	11
Figure 2 Connection of different actors in the overall system.	11

1. Introduction

Given the complex web of communication between the back end and its (software) clients, the corresponding back-end interface is inherently large. The service architecture is used as a guiding principle for the system and the interface are structured by bundling related endpoints (i.e., operations) into services. The services are further grouped based on maturity levels of the respective technologies.

In the following, first the maturity levels are examined, which will be used to group services. Next, the individual services are described in more detail, followed by an overview of the back-end system. Afterwards, a couple of example interactions are presented to illustrate how the system communicates with the (software) clients. Finally, the list of interface specifications is presented in PDF file form, generated from OpenAPI 3 schemas.

2. Maturity Levels

The following maturity levels are identified for BIMprove which will be later refined into services:

- **Mature.** The mature technologies, standard and open. Applicable generally to digital twins without modifications,
- **Experimental.** Best practices and established technologies. Applicable to digital twins with some adjustments and adaptations. We expect that some or all of this functionality will be integrated into Bimsync in the future.
- **Custom.** In-house developed technology. Custom-tailored for BIMprove system, applicable to other systems with significant modifications.

3. Services

Further refining the maturity levels into services which the back end of BIMprove system provides; noted with a slash (“/”) to designate the level.

3.1. Mature / Bimsync

Bimsync is the mature core of our system. Its responsibilities include:

- Managing BIM-related entities.
- Handling the topics (such as construction issues) and their import/export as messages in BIM Collaboration Format (BCF).
- Organization of plan revisions. Each plan revision is imported/exported as an IFC file.

The entities managed by Bimsync are referenced through generally unique identifiers (GUIDs). Furthermore, where applicable, we use unique resource locators (URLs) of the Bimsync’s HTTP interface to retrieve and modify their data.

The management of topics provided by the Bimsync platform are piggy-backed and uses a structured text within topics (e.g., in a body) to store additional information about ongoing business processes. For example, the delivery zone, the entry and the exit zone of a delivery for the truck guidance.

3.2. Experimental / Geometry

This service provides the best practices on how to deal with geometries:

- Serving Collada files (for visualization of the as-planned models in the clients).
- Serving point clouds as POTree or E57 (for visualization of the observations in the clients).
- Conversion of IFC files to Collada format (triggered on plan revisions).

The references to building elements managed in the service “Mature / BIM Sync” are given as GUIDs.

3.3. Experimental / BIM Extended

This service manages the BIM entities which are not widely used, and hence not integrated in the service “Mature / BIM Sync”. However, these entities are already part of the BIM standard and thus generally useful. For example, IfcActor and IfcTask.

The interface of this service encompasses:

- Serving and manipulation of task, cost, actor and zone data as IFC entities. This also includes the complex queries, similar to queries already provided for other entities in BIM Sync.

- Export of all or some of the data as an IFC file.

3.4. Experimental / Localization

This service handles the localization of different entities over time.

The following operations are provided:

- Store the position of an entity.
- Retrieve the position of an instance. For example, this includes the position of the workers, drones, robots, trucks, delivery zones *etc.*

This service is tightly linked to “Experimental / BIM Extended” which is used to store less dynamic data. For example, we introduce the drone as an instance of `IfcActor` in the “Experimental / BIM Extended” to keep the information about the drone. We use “Experimental / Localization” for retrieving the positions of a drone in a given time range (including the latest).

We can also use entities such as `IfcGroup` to model the **cohorts**, *i.e.* a group of people sharing some characteristics. For example, we can introduce the cohort “Workers” to anonymously represent all the workers and store their locations without references to concrete workers.

Moreover, the time and spatial information can be either:

- concrete (a specific date/time or the geolocation, respectively) or
- logical (wider time ranges or logical spatial zones).

The logical specifiers do not imply a connected spatial or temporal area. For example, it can imply “holes” such as a “dangerous zone” which can span multiple floors of a construction site.

3.5. Experimental / Images

This service organizes and searches the images (captured either by UxVs or manually submitted by a worker):

- List images for a given time range and covering one or multiple spots, and
- List images for a given time range taken within a given bounding box.

3.6. Custom / Risk

This service manages the additional data on the risks (fire, fall *etc.*). This includes:

- Querying and updating topics related to risks,
- Querying the risk level based on the given geoposition, and
- Encapsulating the handling of the risk zones (by using the conventions on the calls to “Experimental / BIM Extended”).

The API specification of:

- Mature/Bimsync
- Experimental / Geometry
- Experimental / BIM Extended
- Experimental / Localization
- Custom / UXVs
- Custom / Risk

are available at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4721296>

3.7. Custom / UXVs

This service encapsulates the operations to list and modify unmanned vehicles (UxVs, such as drones and ground robots).

The service provides operations to:

- List and modify UxVs,
- Plan the missions, and
- Transfer the observations from the UxV operating stations.

The missions are modelled as topics using the structured text. This service propagates the calls for managing UxVs to “Experimental / BIM Extended”.

The topics are managed via “Mature / Bimsync”.

An SFTP server is provided as input for point clouds from the UxV operating stations.

4. Overview

4.1. Annuli of Maturity

The following figure illustrates the interface sectors which group the services by the maturity of the underlying technology. The most mature technologies, standard and open, are located in the core circle at the centre. As we go outward, the sectors depict services which are more and more experimental.

Figure 1: Visualisation of maturity levels

4.2. Internal Service Communication

We sketch here the interconnection between the services. The front-end clients need to be aware of these links as many, if not most, non-trivial operations on the system involve multiple services.

For example, relationships in the “Experimental / BIM Extended” can reference other BIM instances via GUIDs managed in “Mature / BIM Sync”. In this case, the client must be aware how to resolve these references. (The back end can help by, say, returning URLs instead of GUIDs so that the client is already aware where to ask for more data in the next step.)

Figure 2 Connection of different actors in the overall system.

5. Data Management

5.1. Anonymization of personal data

Please see BIMprove D5.3 Ethics and Data Management Plan for the details on how we approach the management of the data in a privacy-preserving way.

5.2. Authentication

We use Basic Auth for authentication for simplicity. Further authentication schemas such as Bearer authentication can be used with minimal changes to the system.

5.3. Authorization

We distinguish between two levels of authorization:

- At the service level, and
- At the logic level.

Service level. Each service verifies that the authenticated user is allowed to access it. This is done on the reverse proxy level (e.g., nginx).

Logic level. Apart from the service-level authorization, we also check the authorization within the logic of an endpoint. Namely, for privacy-critical endpoints, the data should be disclosed only to the authorized users, and not all users of the BIMprove system.

For example, only the client for risk escalation and emergency should see the exact position and the identity of the actors on the construction site. This data should be hidden from the other users.

Annex A Schematic of three examples

We examine 3 examples (E1...E3) of interactions between the front-end clients and the services of the BIMprove back-end system. The interactions are depicted as sequence diagrams.

Please see BIMprove D1.1 Overall system design of BIMprove for an overview of the different modules such as BIM@Vehicle, BIM@SiteOffice and BIM@Construction.

E1: Truck Guidance

E2: Deviation As-planned *versus* As-built

E3: On-site Risk Alert

